

COLLEGE STUDENTS' KNOWLEDGE ON SPORTS INJURY PREVENTION AND MANAGEMENT

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ABSTRACT

This study investigated the college students' knowledge on sports injury prevention and management. The study used the descriptive research method to collect data at the University of La Salette, Inc. The population consists of a total of 283 participants, who were selected using stratified random sampling. Data were collected with the aid of questionnaires. According to the statistical analysis, it was found that college students rarely encountered sports injuries during Physical Education class. The most frequent type of injury encountered was a sprain, indicating that college students had a good level of knowledge. Proposed measures to improve the level of knowledge on sports injury prevention and management include prevention through education, educational sessions, ensuring safe equipment and environment, promoting awareness, and providing practical training. It is recommended that comprehensive knowledge on sports injury prevention and management be implemented among students, including specific training programs, seminars, and workshops to help students who have a basic understanding but need to enhance their knowledge.

Keywords: *Sport Injury Prevention and Management, college students, knowledge*

INTRODUCTION

For many years, athletics have been seen as a method to maintain health and fitness, but they encompass more than that. Currently, sports play a crucial role in student's overall growth and development. Engaging in various sports helps impart

essential life skills, such as teamwork, leadership, responsibility, patience, and self-assurance, equipping them to confront challenges in life (Fatima, 2024).

However, not every student knows how to handle the potential injuries they may sustain while participating in various sports. The duty of teaching students how to prevent and manage injuries for various sports-related ailments falls on coaches, administrators, and physical education teachers (Kapil, 2023).

Despite the growing popularity of this sport, the systematic and intensified training of athletes in such games, however, is lacking in basic knowledge and competence for prevention and management of sports injuries techniques. According to Lutter et al. (2021), as with other activities, sports require a specific understanding of prevention and management to reduce injuries and other physical risks. For the purpose of lowering psychological stress, anxiety, and potential risk, athletes should therefore be knowledgeable about injury prevention and care. Furthermore, having a solid understanding of how to prevent and manage sports injuries is fundamental and crucial for athletes, coaches, and everyone else directly or indirectly involved in the sports industry. On the other hand, injuries are preventable and can hinder or ruin an athlete's future.

With the growing popularity of sports, more college students are actively participating in sports. This, in turn, leads to the inevitable occurrence of sports-related injuries. Sports injuries occur frequently, and there have even been cases of sudden death or other serious injuries (Xie & Qiu, 2023). Aksović et al. (2024), found that the most common injuries are ankle sprain and ligament strain. Furthermore, the study of Tang et al. (2020) revealed that injuries occurring outdoors, primarily in non-contact activities, were acute and involved the lower limbs, with sprains and strains being the most commonly injury types.

Not only do these injuries cause physical and psychological harm to the victims, but they also affect their daily life, increasing their psychological and economic burden (Zhang, 2021). Muhammad and Korsheed (2025) concluded that the most common sports injuries during volleyball lessons in students of Physical Education and Sports Sciences are sprains and muscle contractions (muscle spasm). However, on the contrary, according to the study of Videmšek et al. (2023) said that in physical education (PE) at school, most of the participants were injured in one school year. Most injuries were recorded in the lower extremities in the form of wounds. Therefore, knowing common sports injuries in PE class is essential for students as it enables them to engage safely, avoid injuries, and respond appropriately in the event of accidents.

Sports injuries not only threaten athletes' health and safety but also test the professionalism of first aiders on the scene. If students are unfamiliar with first aid and cannot provide prompt and accurate treatment after sports injuries, the injuries may worsen (Zhong, 2023). Additionally, significant findings highlight the importance of knowledge and attitudes toward sports injury prevention. Bakar and Shaharudin (2022): 82.5% of the participants met the knowledge test's requirements and demonstrated a

good and consistent attitude toward sports injury prevention and management. Furthermore, the study of Alnefaie et al. (2025) revealed that the respondents demonstrated a high awareness of sports injury prevention. Moreover, Nurhasan et al. (2024) and Kozina et al. (2022) reported that participants' responses were in the excellent in knowledge on sports injury prevention and management.

According to the National Institute of Arthritis, Musculoskeletal and Skin Disease (2025), efficient management and prevention of sports injuries are essential for enhancing student involvement, reducing time missed due to injury, and fostering overall health. This includes approaches aimed at reducing the risk of injuries through effective training, suitable equipment, and techniques, as well as providing timely and appropriate care for injuries as they occur. Additionally, Coastal Orthopedics (2025) states that preventing and managing sports injuries is vital for maintaining students' health, performance, and durability in their sports activities. Efficient prevention methods reduce the likelihood of injuries, while appropriate management ensures prompt and adequate care, aiding a safe return to sports.

School education is the most effective way to promote the knowledge and skills of sports injury prevention. The student's mastery of sports injury prevention and management knowledge and skills will have a profound impact on their ability to deal with critical events in many fields besides sports (Wang & Huang, 2020).

In fact, according to Johns Hopkins Medicine (2024), approximately 30 million children and teens participate in organized sports in the U.S., and more than 3.5 million injuries occur each year, resulting in some loss of participation time. are experienced by the participants. Almost one-half of all injuries incurred in adolescence are sports-related injuries. By far, the most common injuries are sprains and strains. Although death from a sports injury is rare, the leading cause of death from a sports-related injury is a brain injury. However, in the Philippines, the injury rate for men is 140.63 per 1,000 athlete-exposures (A-E), while the rate for women is 52.24 per 1000. The most common sports-related injuries are sprains. Other common injuries include bruises, strains, joint injuries, and nose bleeds. Most injured people are young, and there are more male injuries than female injuries (Philippine Sports Commission (PSC), 2024).

Furthermore, colleges and universities bear the responsibility to implement the course of "Sports Injury Prevention and Management," transferring skills and acting as a defense of life dignity. The course is designed with consideration for students' safety, physical and mental health, social harmony, and the promotion of knowledge on the prevention and management of sports injuries. It can effectively reduce the harm caused by sports injuries and even save a person's life. Furthermore, it promotes self-protection awareness and develops a training mode that combines teaching, training, and practice. Through practical operations and case analysis, students can better understand theoretical knowledge and apply it in practice, gaining the ability to address real-life problems. Furthermore, sport injury prevention and management are vital for athletes' long-term health, well-being, and continued participation in their chosen sport. By prioritizing prevention and employing effective management strategies, athletes can

minimize injury risks and maximize their potential for success (ChanRobles Virtual Law Library, 2025).

The "Sports Injury Prevention and Management" course is crucial in reducing the risk of injury. Furthermore, it plays a crucial role in enhancing students' knowledge on sports injury prevention and management. In the future, colleges and universities should further optimize the setup and implementation of this course, focusing not only on the practicality and scientific nature of the course content but also on regularly evaluating and updating the teaching methods to maximize educational effectiveness (Zhan et al., 2024).

The efficacy of "Prevention and Management of Sports Injury" courses in reducing the prevalence of school sports injuries has been demonstrated by numerous studies, which established the importance of "Prevention and Management of Sports Injury" knowledge for students. Therefore, this trend highlights the importance of knowledge on sports injury prevention and management among college students of the University of La Salette.

Research Questions

1. What sports injury commonly encountered by the college students during Physical Education class?
2. What is the level of knowledge on sports injury prevention and management of college students?
3. What measures can be proposed to improve the students' knowledge on sports injury prevention and management?

METHODOLOGY

Locale of the Study

The participants of the study were the second-year students enrolled in Physical Activities Toward Health and Fitness (PathFit 004) for the school year 2024-2025 at the University of La Salette, Inc.

Population, Sample Size, and Sampling Method

There were 1,059 students enrolled in Physical Activities Toward Health and Fitness (PathFit-04) for the school year 2024-2025. The participants were selected through stratified random sampling and the representative of the population is determined using Raosoft. Based on Raosoft there were two hundred eighty-three (283) participants of the study, as seen below.

PATHFIT 004			
Departments		Population	Sample
College of Arts and Sciences		35	9
College of Business Education		141	38
College of Teacher Education		86	23
College of Information Technology		33	9
College of Medicine and Allied Medical Program		181	48
College of Nursing Public Health and Midwifery		259	69
College of Engineering and Architecture		254	68
College of Accountancy		70	19
TOTAL		1,059	283

Data Gathering Procedure

The researcher undertaken the necessary protocol in conducting the research. The researcher asked permission from the university president to conduct the research in their retrospective departments. Upon approval of the letter, the researcher asked permission from the department heads and Physical Education instructors/professors of the University of La Salette, Inc. to conduct a study.

The researcher requested to the Office of the Registrar for the student enrollment data for the total population of the participants subsequently sought consent from the participants. And thereafter, the researcher floated the questionnaire during Physical Education subject and were given enough time to complete the questionnaire. After answering the questionnaire, the researcher retrieved, tallied all data gathered, organize, recorded on master sheets, encoded in a spreadsheet for statistical treatments and present in a tabular form.

Research Instrument

A questionnaire was used as a method of data collection. The questionnaire was adapted from the study of Aksovi´el al. (2024) entitled “Sports Injuries in Basketball Players: A Systematic Review” for the part 1 of the research question “what sports injury commonly encountered by the college students during Physical Education class?”. On the other hand, Wang and Huang (2020) entitled “Knowledge and needs for prevention and management of sports injury among high/vocational school students in Taiwan” for the part 2 of the research question “what is the level of knowledge on sports injury prevention and management of college students?”, and frequency and percentage for the analysis of the level of knowledge on sports injury prevention and management of college students. However, the knowledge on sports injury prevention and management section consisted of 25 items which includes 5 items on sports injury prevention, 2 items on sports injury type, 4 items on the principles and methods of sports injury management, 3 items on the principles of extremity and dressing, 2 items on cardiopulmonary resuscitation (CPR), 2 items on hot and cold padding applications, 3 items on heat-related illness in sports, 3 items on traumatic bleeding management, and 1 item on shock management. Thus, 100 points were a full score for correctly answering 25 items. Subjects who correctly

answered more than or equal to 15 items (60 points), were considered as having reasonable understanding of knowledge for "Prevention and Management of Sports Injury". On the other hand, the item was given 4 points when the answer was correct, and given zero points when the answer was incorrect. Furthermore, on the analysis of the level of knowledge on sports injury prevention and management of college students good level of knowledge (score of 1-8 points), intermediate knowledge level (score of 9-16 points), and low level of knowledge (score of 17-25 points).

Data Analysis

To give meaning to the data gathered for the study, the quantitative analysis and computations were computer assisted using SPSS, and the following statistical tool was used:

Mean was used to determine the sports injury commonly encountered by the college students during Physical Education class, and the level of knowledge on sports injury prevention and management of college students.

A 4-point Likert Scale was used for analysis on sports injuries commonly encountered by college students during Physical Education class and the level of knowledge on sports injury prevention and management of college students.

Common Sports Injuries

Number	Range	Interpretation	Rubrics
4	3.25–4.00	Always	This indicates the respondent engages in the activity consistently, meaning it happens every time.
3	2.50–3.25	Often	This signifies a relatively high frequency, suggesting the activity occurs frequently and is a common occurrence.
2	1.75–2.49	Rarely	This suggests the activity occurs infrequently, but not entirely absent.
1	1.00–1.74	Never	This indicates the respondent does not experience or engage in the activity being measured.

Knowledge on Sports Injury Prevention and Management

Number	Range	Interpretation	Rubrics
4	3.25 – 4.00	Very knowledgeable	Exhibit thorough and in-depth comprehension in handling sports injuries

3	2.50 – 3.25	Knowledgeable	Exhibit a lot of awareness, understanding, or skill on handling sports injuries
2	1.75 – 2.49	Slightly knowledgeable	Remembered 50% of safety rules in handling sports injuries
1	1.00 – 1.74	No knowledge	Either forgot the majority of safety rules in handling sports injuries

RESULTS

This presents the analysis and interpretation of data gathered to shed light on the problem. Mainly, the objectives of the study revolve around the specific problems the data were analyzed and interpreted in the following order:

Part 1. Sports Injury Commonly Encountered by the College Students during Physical Education Class

Table 1 presents the mean distribution of sports injury commonly encountered by the college students during Physical Education Class.

Table 1
Mean Distribution on Sports Injury Commonly Encountered by the College Students during Physical Education Class

Dimensions	Mean	Interpretation
Sprain	2.03	Rarely
Abrasions	1.99	Rarely
Strain	1.92	Rarely
Dislocations	1.58	Never
Fractures	1.57	Never
Overall Mean	1.82	Rarely

It shows in Table 1 that the college students rarely encountered sports injuries such as sprain (M=2.03), abrasions (M=1.99) and strain (1.92). It also shows in Table 1 that the college students never encountered sports injuries dislocations (M=1.58) and fractures (M=1.57). With the overall of (M=1.82), this implies that the college students had rarely encountered the sports injuries.

Part 2. Level of Knowledge on Sports Injury Prevention and Management of College Students

Table 2
Mean Distribution on the Level of Knowledge on Sports Injury Prevention and Management

Item No.	Item	Mean	Interpretation
1	Sports protective devices are helpful to stabilize joints. They are used: _____	1.33	No knowledge
2	What do we call a sports injury that damages the ligaments	3.19	Knowledgeable
3	What do we call a sports injury that damages the muscles and tendons	3.12	Knowledgeable
4	What do we call a sports injury that displaces a bone due to collision with external force	3.76	Very knowledgeable
5	The standard procedure to treat a sports injury does not include	2.74	Knowledgeable
6	What is the first-aid method for strains	3.34	Very Knowledgeable
7	The purpose of learning correct sports injury handling principles is not to	2.29	Slightly knowledgeable
8	After injury what should you do to hasten your return to the sports field	2.91	Knowledgeable
9	How to use limb supports correctly	2.91	Knowledgeable
10	Which one of the following is the wrong way to support a limb	2.80	Knowledgeable
11	What is the correct way to use a bandage?	2.05	Slightly knowledgeable
12	What is the cardiac massage frequency per minute when applying CPR to teenagers?	0.64	No knowledge
13	What is the ratio of cardiac massage to breathing per minute when applying CPR to adults?	2.87	Knowledgeable
14	What is the interval between hot/cold compresses?	1.70	No knowledge
15	How long should a hot or cold compress be applied for a sports injury?	2.98	Knowledgeable
16	What is the reason for heatstroke?	3.21	Knowledgeable
17	What is the best preventive action to avoid heatstroke?	3.55	Very knowledgeable
18	What action should not be followed when someone suffers overheating during exercise?	2.61	Knowledgeable

19	What is heatstroke?	2.69	Knowledgeable
20	Which one of the following is not a symptom of heatstroke?	1.24	No knowledge
21	What is the purpose of dressing a bleeding wound?	3.63	Very knowledgeable
22	Which one of the following is the wrong way to treat a bleeding wound?	2.63	Knowledgeable
23	What should be done to treat a severely bleeding wound?	3.38	Very knowledgeable
24	What is shock?	2.28	Slightly knowledgeable
25	Which one of the following methods is the wrong way to treat shock?	2.98	Knowledgeable
Overall Mean		2.67	Knowledgeable

Table 2 presents the level of knowledge on sports injury prevention and management. The college students were very knowledgeable in the items: sports injury that displaces a bone due to collision with external force (M=3.76), purpose of dressing a bleeding wound (M=3.63), best preventive action to avoid heatstroke (M=3.55), treating a severely bleeding wound (M=3.38), and first-aid method for strains (M=3.34).

It is also stated in Table 2, that the college students were knowledgeable in the items: reason for heatstroke (M=3.21), sports injury that damages the ligaments (M=3.19), sports injury that damages the muscles and tendons (M=3.12), application of hot or cold compress for a sports injury and wrong methods to treat shock (M=2.98) respectively, hastening the return to the sports field and using limb supports correctly (M=2.91) respectively, ratio of cardiac massage to breathing per minute when applying CPR to adults (M=2.87), wrong way to support a limb (M=2.80), standard procedure to treat a sports injury (M=2.74), heatstroke (M=2.69), wrong way to treat a bleeding wound (M=2.63), action should not be followed when someone suffers overheating during exercise (M=2.61), learning correct sports injury handling principles (M=2.28), shock (M=2.28), and limb supports correctly (M=2.05).

Furthermore, Table 2 also presents that college students have no knowledge on the following items: hot/cold compresses (M=1.70), sports protective devices (M=1.33), heat stroke (M=1.24), and cardiac massage frequency per minute when applying CPR to teenagers (M=0.64). With an overall (M=2.67), this implies that the college students were knowledgeable on the sports injury prevention and management.

Table 3
Analysis of the Level of Knowledge on Sports Injury Prevention and Management of College Students

Category	Frequency	Percentage
Low Knowledge Level	16	5.7
Intermediate Knowledge	105	37.1
Good Level of Knowledge	162	57.2
Total	283	100

Table 3 discloses the summary table of the level of knowledge on sports injury prevention and management. The analysis of the individual values shows that 162 or 57.2% of the college students had a good level of knowledge (score of 1-8 points), 105 or 37.1% had an intermediate knowledge level (score of 9-16 points), and only 16 or 5.7% had a low level of knowledge (score of 17-25 points). This implies that the college students had a good level of knowledge on the sports injury prevention and management.

Part 3. Proposed Measures to Improve the Students' Knowledge on Sports Injury Prevention and Management

Title: College Students' Knowledge on Sports Injury Prevention and Management

Program Rationale

Based on the findings of the study, the results showed that the majority of college students revealed a good level of knowledge on sports injury prevention and management (162, 57.2%) and intermediate knowledge (105, 37.1 %). However, improving student knowledge of sports injury prevention and management is crucial by reducing injuries and promoting proper management of those PathFit 004 students who have low knowledge level (16, 5.7 %).

Hence, education empowers students to identify risks, implement preventative, understand basic first aid, and recognize the importance of rehabilitation, ultimately leading to a safe return to sports after an injury.

Component	Objective	Strategy (Key Activities)	Human Resources & Budget	Success Indicators	Timeline
	To equip individuals with the knowledge, necessary to minimize the risk of injury during physical education	- Educate students on proper warm-up and cool-down procedures to minimize muscle strains, sprains and abrasions.		-Reduced incidence and severity of injuries. -Increased students' knowledge	

Prevention through education	class. This involves promoting awareness of potential hazards, teaching safe participation practices, and fostering a culture of injury prevention.	-Teach safe techniques including proper body mechanics and equipment usage.	-Physical Education Instructor -PATHFIT 004 students	towards preventive measures and management. -Consistent adoption of safe behaviors (like proper warm-ups and cool-down)	- Medium term (weeks to months) (6 weeks)
Educational sessions	To equip participants with the knowledge and skills to minimize the risk of sports-related injuries and effectively manage them when they occur.	-Organize regular workshops and seminars. -Develop and promote online platforms with educational materials, including videos articles, and infographics. -Incorporate injury prevention and management topics into existing physical education curricula and training programs, ensuring students understand the importance of these aspects from the outset.	-Sports medicine professionals -Physical Education Instructors -PATHFIT 004 students Budget: (token and food for seminar/workshop) (3,000)	-Students demonstrate greater understanding of injury prevention and management. - A statistically significant decrease in the number of reported injuries during Physical Education class. - Students' develop a stronger sense of competence and self-efficacy in their ability to handle challenges related to injury.	-Short term (immediate) (7 days)
Safe equipment and environment	To minimize the risk of injury by creating a safer playing field and reducing exposure to hazards. This involves ensuring proper protective gear, maintaining equipment, and establishing a	-Ensure that students use the correct size and fit of protective gear appropriate for their spot. -Maintain safe playing fields and facilities, including proper lighting and equipment.	-Physical Education Instructor -PATHFIT 004 students	- A lower number of sports injuries overall points to the effectiveness of correctly sized and fitted gear. - Reduction in sports-related injuries, which can be measured by	-Short term (immediate)

	safe playing environment.	-Enforce safety rules and guidelines during class, practices and games.		lower injury rates, decreased severity of injuries, and fewer management issues. Key factors contributing to this success are proper facility maintenance, access to and use of appropriate safety equipment.	(1 day)
Promoting awareness	To reduce the incidence and severity of sports-related injuries	<p>-Launch campaigns through posters, social media, and campus announcements to highlight the importance of sports injury prevention and management.</p> <p>-Share stories of athletes who have benefited from preventative measures or who have successfully recovered from injuries through proper management.</p> <p>-Encourage peer-to-peer learning and mentorship programs where experienced athletes share their knowledge with their peers.</p>	<p>-Physical Education Instructor</p> <p>-PATHFIT 004 students</p> <p>-Peer group</p> <p>-Athletes</p> <p>Budget: 2,000.00 for posters</p>	<p>- Students demonstrate a greater understanding of common sports injuries, their causes, and effective prevention and management strategies.</p> <p>- Students consistently use safety gear, perform proper warm-ups and cool-downs, and follow the correct techniques for their sports.</p> <p>-A significant decrease in the number of students experiencing sports-related injuries, and a reduction in the severity of those injuries that do occur.</p>	

<p>Practical training</p>	<p>To equip individuals with the knowledge and skills necessary to minimize the risk of injuries, effectively manage them when they occur, and facilitate safe return to sports participation</p>	<p>-Provide mandatory or optional first aid training for all students, especially those involved in sports. This training should cover basic wound care, injury assessment, and emergency procedures.</p> <p>Offer coaching on proper techniques for various sports, emphasizing alignment, posture, and movement patterns to minimize injury risk.</p>	<p>-Sports medicine professionals</p> <p>-Physical Education Instructors</p> <p>-Students of the University of La Salette</p> <p>Budget:</p> <p>2,000.00 for posters</p>	<p>- Students demonstrate knowledge and practical application of injury prevention techniques, and effective assessment and management of injuries.</p>	<p>-Long term (months to year)</p> <p>(1 to 5 months)</p>
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DISCUSSION

The main objectives of the study were to determine the knowledge on sports injury prevention and management of the college students of the University of La Salette, Inc. Based on the data acquired retrospectively from the questionnaire, the study emphasizes the sports injuries commonly encountered by college students during physical Education class and knowledge on sports injury prevention and management.

I. Sports Injuries Commonly Encountered by the College Students during Physical Education Class

This study showed that the college students had rarely encountered sports injuries, this implies that sports injuries like sprains, abrasions, and strains were rarely encountered by the college students. On the other hand, sports injuries in college students can have a significant impact both their physical and mental well-being, as well as their academic performance. The consequences can range from missed classes and assignments to difficulties concentrating and even mental health challenges.

This tendency is in agreement with the study of Aksović et al, (2024), found that the most common injuries are ankle sprain and ligament strain. Furthermore, the study of Tang et al. (2020) revealed that injuries occurring outdoors, primarily in non-contact

activities, were acute and involved the lower limbs, with sprains and strains being the most commonly injury types.

Moreover, Muhammad and Korsheed (2025) concluded that the most common sports injuries during volleyball lessons in students of Physical Education and Sports Sciences are sprains and muscle contractions (muscle spasm). However, on the contrary, according to the study of Videmšek et al. (2023) said that in physical education (PE) at school, most of the participants were injured in one school year.

Most injuries were recorded in the lower extremities in the form of wounds. Therefore, knowing common sports injuries in PE class is essential for students as it enables them to engage safely, avoid injuries, and respond appropriately in the event of accidents. This understanding enables them to establish healthy routines, comprehend their bodies, and recognize the significance of information on preventing and managing sports injuries.

II. Level of Knowledge on Sports Injury Prevention and Management of College Students

In the study of the level of knowledge on sports injury prevention and management, the majority of college students at the University of La Salette, Inc. demonstrated good knowledge, which is categorized as a positive finding. However, it is indicated that college students were very knowledgeable on sports injury that displaces a bone due to collision with external force, the purpose of dressing a bleeding wound, the best preventive action to avoid heatstroke, treating a severely bleeding wound, and the first-aid method for strains. According to the study of Bakar and Shaharudin (2022): 82.5% of the participants met the knowledge test's requirements and demonstrated a good and consistent attitude toward sports injury prevention and management. Furthermore, the study of Alnefaie et al. (2025) revealed that the respondents demonstrated a high awareness of sports injury prevention. Moreover, Nurhasan et al. (2024) and Kozina et al. (2022) reported that participants' responses were in the excellent in knowledge on sports injury prevention and management.

According to the National Institute of Arthritis, Musculoskeletal and Skin Disease (2025), efficient management and prevention of sports injuries are essential for enhancing student involvement, reducing time missed due to injury, and fostering overall health. This includes approaches aimed at reducing the risk of injuries through effective training, suitable equipment, and techniques, as well as providing timely and appropriate care for injuries as they occur. Additionally, Coastal Orthopedics (2025) states that preventing and managing sports injuries is vital for maintaining students' health, performance, and durability in their sports activities. Efficient prevention methods reduce the likelihood of injuries, while appropriate management ensures prompt and adequate care, aiding a safe return to sports.

These indicated that teachers were crucial knowledge sources for students; thus, it is essential to develop comprehensive training on sports injury prevention and

management to enhance students' understanding to avoid injuries from excessive practice. Thus, teaching students' injury prevention techniques and management, along with enhancing motivation for learning and practical first-aid skills, must be essential components of sport injury management education

III. Proposed Measures to Improve the Students' Knowledge on Sports Injury Prevention and Management

The proposed measures to improve the students' knowledge on sports prevention and management includes prevention through education, educational sessions, safe equipment and environment, promoting awareness, practical training.

Conclusions

The study evaluated the college students' knowledge on sports injury prevention and management. Based on the results of the study, the following conclusions are drawn:

Majority of the college students' rarely encountered sports injury during Physical Education class. Therefore, sports injuries seldom arise because of students lack readiness and knowledge on sports injury prevention and management during Physical Education class.

The majority of the college students had a good level of knowledge on sports injury prevention and management. This asserts that the students' personal experiences with sports activities during Physical Education class lead them to seek information and develop practical knowledge about prevention and management.

The proposed measures to improve the level of knowledge on sports injury prevention and management include prevention through education, educational sessions, safe equipment and environment, promoting awareness and practical training.

Recommendations

It was necessary to strengthen the sports injury prevention and management of the college students'.

In light of the foregoing results, conclusions, and proposed measures to improve the level of knowledge on sports injury prevention and management, the following recommendations are offered:

1. Sports injuries in physical education (PE) classes highlight the need for proactive injury prevention strategies and management. These strategies should focus on addressing common types of injuries, such as sprains, abrasions, and strains. Implementing comprehensive knowledge on sports injury prevention and management among students and teachers can significantly reduce the incidence and severity of injuries.

2. The higher risk groups of sports injury considered specific training programs or seminars and workshop focus on “Sports Injury Prevention Management” highly needed indicating students who have a basic understanding but need to enhance their knowledge on sports protective devices, learning correct sports injury handling principles, correct way to use bandage, applying CPR, technique on hot/cold compresses, treatment of heat stroke and sports related shock.

3. To encourage the implementers to adopt necessary measures in improving the knowledge of the college students on sports injury prevention and management.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

Before undertaking the study, the researcher requested the participants’ informed consent. The researcher followed all ethical protocols: maintaining the privacy of data, protecting confidentiality, and ensuring that no personal identifying information was used. The participants were expected to willingly participate in the study and were given all necessary information to make an informed decision about participating. Participants were protected by keeping the information confidential, and no questionnaires contained any of the participants’ names. Participants were also assured that any information obtained would be used only for the purposes indicated in the objectives and that their consent would be sought before revealing their information for any other purposes.

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